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THE MAIN PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF GREEN ZONES OF THE CITY

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1-section. "Development of urban areas formation and integrated development of architecture and urban environment."

Annotation. A modern city is an ecosystem in which landscaping plays an important role. This article provides information about the architectural concept of improving the landscaping system for the city, including the basic architectural and planning principles, techniques and content of elements of the landscaping system.

Аннотация. Современный город представляет собой экосистему, в которой озеленение выполняет важную роль. В данной статье даны сведения о архитектурной концепции совершенствования системы озеленения для города, включающие основные архитектурно-планировочные принципы, приемы и содержание элементов системы озеленения.

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy shahar obodonlashtirish muhim rol o'ynaydigan ekotizimni ifodalaydi. Ushbu maqolada shahar uchun obodonlashtirish tizimini takomillashtirishning me'moriy konsepsiyasi, shu jumladan obodonlashtirish tizimining asosiy me'moriy va rejalashtirish tamoyillari, texnikasi va elementlarining mazmuni haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Ключевые слова: система озеленения города, благоустройство, планировочная структура, сквер, бульвар, озелененные территории, национальный парк, градостроительные условия, зелёные насаждения.

Key words: city landscaping system, improvement, planning structure, square, boulevard, landscaped, areas, national park, urban planning conditions green spaces.

Kalit so'zlar: shaharni obodonlashtirish tizimi, obodonlashtirish, rejalashtirish tuzilishi, maydonlar, bulvarlar, ko'kalamzorlashtirilgan hududlar, milliy bog', shaharsozlik sharoitlari, yashil maydonlar.

Green spaces, organically included in the composition of buildings, improve the structural and planning and architectural and artistic advantages of the city, help to create an expressive three-dimensional appearance of the settlement, its picturesque silhouette.

The greening system of the city should ensure relatively uniform placement of plantings on residential territories, in residential areas and microdistricts, in public and cultural centers, in industrial and sanitary protection zones.

In cities, more than 50% of the territory, and in microdistricts up to 70% of the total area is allocated to green spaces, which unite individual buildings, structures and their groups into ensembles of a microdistrict or quarter and, together with flooding of the territory, improvement of the relief, engineering improvement, form a modern city. [1]

In a modern city, flexible planning structures are used that can respond to

changing needs and conditions, so the systems of green areas of the city are constantly complicated, and their individual elements are increasingly differentiated. If in a small city, as a rule, there is one multifunctional park and several city gardens, boulevards and squares, then as the city increases, the differentiation of objects of its landscaping system by types, size, functions increases.

The following factors influence the formation of the green space system:

- ratio of built-up and open urban areas;
- the share of existing green spaces, their quality and place in the planning structure of the settlement;
- value and number of individual landscaped areas and their functional role;
- landscape features of the object;
- transport and pedestrian accessibility of green areas.

The relationship between the arrays of urban and suburban green areas is carried out

using a continuous chain of boulevards, embankments, alleys, green lanes along highways, special protective forest lanes, etc.

The variety of applied landscaping systems of the city is due to the presence of specific urban planning conditions - the location of the city in the group settlement system; national economic profile; value and accepted zoning scheme of the territory; placement of public centers, residential buildings, industry; architectural and planning solution of the territory; diagram of transport highways; the possibility of organizing a unified system of green spaces of the city and its green belt, the prospect of development. An important role is assigned to natural-climatic, sanitary-hygienic, landscape-ecological, physical-geographical and some other factors. [2]

The formation and development of urban green spaces is influenced by the natural features of this area: climate, relief, existing vegetation, soil, the presence of water bodies, geological and hydrological conditions. Among the climatic characteristics, radiation, temperature, wind modes, the amount of precipitation, the speed and direction of winds are of paramount importance. The degree of influence of various factors on landscaping techniques changes on a case-by-case basis. At the same time, a special role is given to a comprehensive assessment of the existing state of the urban environment.

Depending on urban planning and natural conditions, the city's landscaping system can be in the form of green "spots" of several large green arrays evenly scattered throughout the city - wedges that penetrate the city center; water-green diameter (systems of parks, boulevards, open spaces along the floodplain of the river crossing the city); one or more strips of green space stretching along the development, sometimes the strips are located transversely, dividing the city into segments; green areas surrounding individual urban areas. [3]

Green spaces, organically included in the composition of the development, improve the structural, planning and architectural and

artistic advantages of the city, help to create an expressive volumetric and spatial appearance of the city, a picturesque silhouette.

The influence of natural factors on the formation of the city is especially noticeable in new cities of small size that have a landscape dominant - for example, a water-green diameter, which becomes the main compositional axis of the city.

The city's landscaping system should ensure relatively uniform placement of plantations in residential areas, in residential areas and microdistricts, in public and cultural centers, in industrial and sanitary protection zones.

The formation of a system of urban green spaces is influenced by: the ratio of built-up and open urban areas; the share of existing plantations, their quality and place in the planning structure of the city; value and fraction of individual landscaped areas, their functional role; landscape features; transport and pedestrian accessibility.

When constructing a landscaping system, the following general requirements must be met:

- uniform placement of landscaping facilities for common use in residential areas, in public city centers, in industrial and municipal storage areas, on highways and streets;

- integration into a single system of urban and suburban objects by a network of landscaped pedestrian routes, embankments, boulevards;

- interconnection of the urban landscape with the relief of the surrounding environment, water bodies, buildings, structures and equipment of the welfare device;

- inclusion of the greening system in the complex of measures for nature protection, environmental improvement.

In order to achieve the best health-improving effect and to create normal plant development conditions, the urban green space system must take into account the existing state of the environment, as well as the possibility of its change in connection

with the proposed development of the city. The results of the environmental assessment are applied in the form of graphic diagrams to the plans of urban areas. A comprehensive assessment is given by combining the schemes of each of the analyses performed. This method is used successfully in the design of planning solutions.

In dry and hot areas of the south, plantings are vital as they mitigate adverse weather conditions, especially in co-dating with water bodies. The creation of a system of green areas in southern cities with normal irrigation is proceeding quickly, and only 10-15 years to get a positive microclimatic effect from plantations.

In cities with significant sources of pollution, it is necessary to use scientifically based schemes for the placement and organization of sanitary protection zones, to carry out landscaping of industrial, communal and transport territories.

The emergence of new cities, as a rule, is associated with the development of industry, and their landscaping has its own characteristics, determined by the specifics of specific technological processes used in this production.

The creation of green areas in cities with unfavorable natural conditions is complicated by the laboriousness of carrying out the necessary planting work and the subsequent care of plants. In oasis cities, the artificially created landscaping system is in conditions of excessive insolation, so it is advisable to place plants compactly in relatively small areas near housing, shopping and public centers, in the form of boulevards and alleys along canals, ditches, providing shading of pedestrian links between residential complexes and urban areas. centers of attraction.

Cities located among valuable agricultural land develop green space systems by combining economic and recreational functions.

In the system of urban green spaces, areas can be allocated for short-term recreation, mainly in the forest park belt and suburban area. At the same time, convenient

accessibility, good sanitary and hygienic and microclimatic conditions, picturesque landscape should be taken into account. Areas for everyday recreation are located near housing, city centers and places of employment.

One of the basic principles of modern ecology states that the landscape is most resistant to disturbances, in which transformed and natural areas alternate, therefore, in green areas, especially in arrays of significant sizes, special protected areas are allocated.

In the territories of parks, forest parks, national and natural parks, zones for the protection of cultural monuments and nature, it is not allowed to place buildings, structures and communications that are not related to the service of visitors.

In the master plan for the development of the city, the formation of a system of green spaces is provided for an estimated period of 25-30 years. Periodic stabilization of the city's borders makes it possible to strengthen the trees and shrubs of the green belt, restrains the growth of development and the merger of populated areas. At the end of the estimated period, the city's border expands due to the annexation of territories located behind the established green belt. [4].

The city must be considered as a holistic anthropogenic complex, where society must be provided and preserved for posterity, favorable conditions for further existence. Not to the detriment of the environmental component, the functionality of the urban environment has been strengthened, due to the streamlining of economic activities and the expansion of various types of services. Professional contacts and corporate meetings, communication in the natural environment, sports, active games of teenagers, cycling on equipped paths, participation in educational and creative processes in the open air, attending impromptu concerts and performances in open areas - these and many other developing scenarios are envisaged in modern cities [4].

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